

Conformational study of 1,2-dioxane molecule and its halogenated derivatives from the semiempirical AM1 and PM3 molecular orbital methods – a comparative analysis

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A conformational study of 1,2-dioxane and several halogenated derivatives is performed through the employment of the molecular orbital theory. Semiempirical AM1 and PM3 methods are applied and the resulting numerical values are discussed in a comparative fashion. Besides, theoretical results are analyzed in comparison with available experimental and *ab initio* data. The different electronic factors determining the stability of the conformers are discussed and they allow one to rationalize the differential stabilities of the different conformers.

A wide variety of molecular compounds of marine origin (coming from sea urchins and sponges) with an acetate or propionate main chain joined at the C₃ position of the 1,2-dioxane ring have been isolated¹. It was determined that they have a remarkable antimicrobial activity² and they may correspond to known bicyclic or acyclic structures. One of these isolated compounds, pricin A of *Prianos* sp.³, which was identified as *Muquibilin* (Fig. 1, R = H) is a nortriterpenoid⁴ which is responsible for the fertilization inhibition and fracture of the sea urchin⁴. It was also possible to isolate from the solution extract, the corresponding methyl ester of pricin A (Fig. 1, R = Me). Its remarkable antimicrobial action led to the conclusion that it is more active than the tetracyclin antibiotic, although it is inactive regarding the Gram-negative bacteria³. At the same time, this compound exerts a strong antimicrobial action which is more effective than micostatin.

Fig. 1

Two cyclic compounds containing a bisabolene skeleton, qingzhaosu A (Fig. 2) and qingzhaosu C (Fig. 3) isolated from the plant roots (*Artabotrys uncinatus* or *A. hexapetalus*) are employed in malaria treatments⁵.

Fig. 2

Thus the most relevant conclusion regarding the intimate molecular structure-biological activity relationship is the existence of a six-member ring with a peroxidic bond which is responsible for antibacterial, antimalarial or/and antimicrobial pharmacological action.

Fig. 3

This paper deals with the theoretical calculations based on the molecular orbital theory applied for studying the conformational features of 1,2-dioxane and its di- and tetra-halogenated derivatives. We discuss the stability order of the different conformers arising from the semiempirical AM1 and PM3 methods and results are compared with previous *ab initio* calculations published⁶. We find that for the whole set of conformers the AM1 method underestimates the peroxidic O–O bond length of the studied molecules around 12%, while the PM3 method, which was developed more

recently, describes numerically this bond length in a more suitable way. The degree of accuracy of both the semiempirical methods is discussed with respect to the 1,2-dioxane molecular structure.

Although literature registers that *trans*-conformations of 1,3-dioxanes and 1,4-dioxanes are the most stable ones, we have also studied both *cis* and *trans* disubstituted isomers since there complete experimental data for 1,2-dioxanes structures are not available. In fact, Caballeira *et al.*⁶ reported some partial experimental results for the 1,2-dioxane and two substituted dioxane molecules. Thus, we have decided to make the comparison with the experimental data corresponding to the basic skeleton geometry.

Table 1. Geometrical parameters for 1,2-dioxane molecule, calculated with the AM1 and PM3 methods

	AM1		PM3	
	Twist	Chair	Twist	Chair
Bond length (Å)				
O ₁ -O ₂	1.286	1.290	1.536	1.574
C ₆ -O ₁	1.449	1.447	1.394	1.391
C ₃ -O ₂	1.450	1.447	1.395	1.391
C ₃ -C ₄	1.518	1.518	1.533	1.531
C ₄ -C ₅	1.515	1.517	1.516	1.519
C ₆ -C ₅	1.519	1.518	1.533	1.530
C ₃ -H ₇	1.119	1.119	1.106	1.107
C ₃ -H ₈	1.119	1.120	1.106	1.105
Bond angle (deg)				
C ₆ -O ₁ -O ₂	112.72	112.42	108.54	108.58
C ₆ -C ₅ -C ₄	110.81	110.15	111.51	109.50
C ₃ -C ₄ -C ₅	110.31	110.85	111.04	110.21
C ₃ -O ₂ -O ₁	112.86	112.51	108.45	108.52
O ₂ -C ₃ -C ₄	111.77	110.18	114.89	113.86
O ₁ -C ₆ -C ₅	111.60	109.92	114.65	113.89
H ₈ -C ₃ -O ₂	102.91	103.20	109.58	110.94
H ₇ -C ₃ -O ₂	108.30	109.90	100.42	100.68
H ₇ -C ₃ -H ₈	110.11	110.71	107.93	108.35
Torsion angle (deg)				
C ₆ -C ₅ -C ₄ -C ₃	51.88	47.05	51.51	48.99
C ₆ -O ₁ -O ₂ -C ₃	72.04	-66.30	72.75	-63.49
O ₁ -O ₂ -C ₃ -C ₄	-35.12	60.26	-39.25	59.99
C ₅ -C ₄ -C ₃ -O ₂	-25.88	-49.89	-19.34	-55.63
O ₂ -O ₁ -C ₆ -C ₅	-40.28	61.12	-38.87	61.00
C ₄ -C ₅ -C ₆ -O ₁	-21.13	50.65	-19.90	-56.22

Results and discussion

1,2-Dioxane :

The optimized geometry in its twist and chair conformations was determined via the semiempirical AM1 and PM3 methods and the most significant results are given in Table 1. The optimization process was made without any restriction regarding the molecular symmetry, and numerical results predict the twist conformer to be the most stable

one according to the MNDO-PM3 methods and chair for AM1 (Table 5). When comparing both the isomers calculated with the AM1 method, these have a bond length difference of 0.004 Å for O–O (1.290 vs 1.286 Å, 0.003 Å for C–O and the C–H bond does not present any difference and its value is 1.119 Å. The bond angle differences data are : O–C–C bond angle is 1.59° (11.18° vs 111.77°), H–C–H is 0.79° (110.89° vs 110.11°), and the C–O–O–C dihedral angle is 5.74° (72.04° vs 66.30°). The energy difference between both conformers turns to be 2.2 kcal mol⁻¹.

In a similar manner, the application of the PM3 method shows that the twist geometry is the lowest energetic one and regarding the AM1 method an improvement of the heats of formation and the description of the peroxidic O–O bond lengths were obtained. So, they approach quite well to the experimental values. The energy difference between both the conformers is 7.7 kcal mol⁻¹.

Fig. 4. Optimized geometry for the chair and twist conformations via AM1 method.

3,3,6,6-Tetrafluoro-1,2-dioxane :

We have optimized the twist and chair geometry of these conformers (Figs. 4 and 5) by means of the semiempirical methods, which predict an energy minimum for the twist conformer for the AM1 method and the chair conformer for the MNDO and PM3 methods (Table 5). The data are presented in Table 2. Regarding the bond lengths, the comparison between different conformers reveals that, though peroxidic O–O bond lengths are the same (1.279 Å) according to the AM1 method, this value is significantly shorter than the experimental one (1.47 Å). This difference is attributable to the underestimation made by the AM1 method for the peroxide chemical bond lengths. However,

Fig. 5. Optimized geometry of the 3,3,6,6-tetrafluoro-1,2-dioxane calculated with the AM1 method.

C–O bond lengths do not present differences (1.455 Å) and also C–F are equal (1.364 Å). The largest differences between both the conformers take place in the bond angles.

Fig. 6. Optimized geometry of the 3,3,6,6-tetrachloro-1,2-dioxane calculated with the AM1 method.

O–C–C is 1.13° (107.37° vs 106.24°), F–C–F is 0.49° (105.4° vs 105.89°), and C–O–O–C dihedral angle is 5.38 (69.75° vs 64.37°). Here the energy difference is just $1.0 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$. PM3 method also predicts the chair conformation to be the most stable one, although the energy difference is rather low, i.e. $0.28 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

3,3,6,6-Tetrachloro-1,2-dioxane :

Table 2 embraces the calculated geometry parameters of the twist and chair conformers (Figs. 4 and 6) calculated with the AM1 method. We do not see large differences while comparing bond lengths and bond angles. The O–O

Fig. 7. Optimized geometry for the chair and twist conformations via PM3 method.

Fig. 8. Optimized geometry of the 3,6-difluoro-1,2-dioxane calculated with the AM1 method.

bond lengths do not present any difference and the value is 1.278 Å, the C–O bond length difference is 0.001 Å (1.459 vs 1.460 Å), C–Cl is 0.005 Å (1.767 vs 1.761 Å), O–C–C bond angle is 0.95° (110.17° vs 109.22°), Cl–C–Cl is 0.07° (109.43° vs 109.50°) and the C–O–O–C dihedral angle is 7.91° (71.69° vs 63.78°). The energy difference is 0.1 kcal mol⁻¹.

Table 2. Geometrical parameters for 3,3,6,6-tetrafluoro-(tetrachloro)-1,2-dioxane molecule, calculated with the AM1 method

	4F		4Cl	
	Twist	Chair	Twist	Chair
Bond length (Å)				
O ₁ -O ₂	1.279	1.279	1.278	1.278
C ₆ -O ₁	1.455	1.455	1.459	1.460
C ₃ -O ₂	1.454	1.455	1.460	1.459
C ₃ -C ₄	1.544	1.543	1.532	1.529
C ₄ -C ₅	1.512	1.511	1.516	1.515
C ₆ -C ₅	1.543	1.542	1.530	1.527
C ₃ -X ₇	1.364	1.363	1.767	1.761
C ₃ -X ₈	1.364	1.363	1.766	1.761
Bond angle (deg)				
C ₆ -O ₁ -O ₂	113.42	113.41	113.39	114.28
C ₆ -C ₅ -C ₄	110.03	110.60	109.92	110.50
C ₃ -C ₄ -C ₅	109.66	110.78	109.72	110.86
C ₃ -O ₂ -O ₁	113.26	113.40	113.55	114.22
O ₂ -C ₃ -C ₄	112.46	111.03	110.17	109.22
O ₁ -C ₆ -C ₅	112.38	110.89	110.43	109.34
X ₇ -C ₃ -X ₈	105.40	105.89	109.43	109.50
X ₇ -C ₃ -O ₂	105.59	106.77	104.09	111.49
X ₈ -C ₃ -O ₂	101.53	101.30	110.58	104.31
Torsion angle (deg)				
C ₆ -C ₅ -C ₄ -C ₃	53.16	44.45	57.02	48.57
C ₆ -O ₁ -O ₂ -C ₃	69.75	-64.37	71.69	-63.78
O ₁ -O ₂ -C ₃ -C ₄	-38.67	58.29	-41.20	58.05
C ₅ -C ₄ -C ₃ -O ₂	-23.00	-47.77	-30.42	-49.75
O ₂ -O ₁ -C ₆ -C ₅	-33.18	58.97	-30.42	58.53
C ₄ -C ₅ -C ₆ -O ₁	-28.21	-48.30	-32.40	-49.99

Fig. 9. Optimized geometry of the 3,6-dichloro-1,2-dioxane calculated with the AM1 method.

3,6-Difluoro-1,2-dioxane :

The results for the geometry optimization of the two conformers (twist and chair, respectively) corresponding to the *trans* isomers (Figs. 7 and 8) calculated with the AM1 method are displayed in Table 3. In Table 4 we give the enthalpies of formation of all the conformers studied. The comparison of the numerical data given in Table 3 reveals that O–O bond lengths (1.286 Å and C–O bond lengths (1.446 Å) have not any difference, while C–F has a small 0.001 Å difference (1.370 vs 1.371 Å), O–C–C bond angles 1.46° (110.19° vs 11.65°), H–C–F is 0.22° (110.80° vs 110.58°) and the C–O–O–C torsion angle is 7.91° (71.41 vs 63.59°). The energy difference is equal to 4.0 kcal mol⁻¹.

Table 3. Geometrical parameters for 3,6-difluoro(dichloro)-1,2-dioxane molecule, calculated with the AM1 method

	2F		2Cl	
	Twist	Chair	Twist	Chair
Bond length (Å)				
O ₁ -O ₂	1.286	1.286	1.280	1.287
C ₆ -O ₁	1.446	1.446	1.461	1.439
C ₃ -O ₂	1.446	1.445	1.458	1.440
C ₃ -C ₄	1.536	1.534	1.521	1.521
C ₅ -C ₄	1.512	1.512	1.514	1.515
C ₆ -C ₅	1.536	1.534	1.521	1.521
C ₃ -H ₈	1.127	1.127	1.118	1.122
C ₃ -X ₇	1.371	1.370	1.767	1.772
Bond angle (deg)				
C ₆ -O ₁ -O ₂	113.34	114.16	113.32	115.09
C ₆ -C ₅ -C ₄	110.50	110.69	110.15	110.72
C ₃ -C ₄ -C ₅	110.51	110.93	110.21	111.26
C ₃ -O ₂ -O ₁	113.36	114.14	113.38	115.11
O ₂ -C ₃ -C ₄	111.63	110.37	111.21	110.51
O ₁ -C ₆ -C ₅	111.65	110.19	110.84	110.66
O ₂ -C ₃ -X ₇	104.45	105.51	106.05	112.53
O ₂ -C ₃ -H ₈	103.77	103.52	107.70	102.80
X ₇ -C ₃ -H ₈	110.58	110.80	106.56	106.32
X ₇ -C ₃ -C ₄	112.87	113.77	111.89	111.46
C ₄ -C ₃ -H ₈	112.86	112.16	113.04	112.88
Torsion angle (deg)				
C ₆ -C ₅ -C ₄ -C ₃	52.50	45.96	55.20	46.28
C ₆ -O ₁ -O ₂ -C ₃	71.41	-63.50	70.43	-60.65
O ₁ -O ₂ -C ₃ -C ₄	-38.89	57.42	-28.69	55.44
C ₅ -C ₄ -C ₃ -O ₂	-24.43	-48.28	-32.82	-47.88
O ₂ -O ₁ -C ₆ -C ₅	-36.98	58.09	-42.71	55.98
C ₄ -C ₅ -C ₆ -O ₁	-24.34	-48.76	-19.98	-48.14

The geometries exhibited in Table 3 refer to the chair conformation with the substituents at the axial-axial position, which is found to be the most stable one. PM3 method also predicts the chair conformation as the most stable one and it gives larger differences for the O–O (0.008 Å and C–C distances (1.543 vs 1.551 Å), while the C–F distances are equal but shorter than that predicted by the AM1 method. The energy difference is 8.9 kcal mol⁻¹.

Table 4. Heats of formation (kcal mol⁻¹) for the 3,6-disubstituted-1,2-dioxane isomers

Isomers	AM1		MNDO-PM3	
	Chair	Twist	Chair	Twist
3,6-Difluoro-1,2-dioxane				
<i>a-a</i>	-135.56	-135.17	-135.23	-132.96
<i>a-e</i>	-133.48	-131.53	-130.53	-126.35
<i>e-e</i>	-131.58	-135.17	-126.80	-132.96
3,6-Dichloro-1,2-dioxane				
<i>a-a</i>	-40.28	-39.04	-47.78	-45.39
<i>a-e</i>	-37.18	-34.34	-43.33	-37.96
<i>e-e</i>	-35.11	-39.04	-39.59	-45.39

3,6-Dichloro-1,2-dioxane :

The optimization results for the geometry of the twist and chair conformers at the *trans* (axial-axial) structures (Figs. 7 and 9) are presented in the Table 3. We give the heats of formation of the whole set of studied conformers. The comparison among the most stable conformers shows that the difference in O–O bond is 0.007 Å (1.287 vs 1.280 Å), C–O is 0.018 Å (1.458 vs 1.440 Å), C–Cl is 0.005 Å (1.767 vs 1.772 Å), O–C–C bond angles is 0.70° (111.21° vs 110.51°), the H–C–Cl is 0.24° (106.56° vs 106.32°), and the torsion angle is 9.78° (70.43° vs 60.65°). The energy difference is 1.2 kcal mol⁻¹.

The PM3 method is coincident with the AM1 method regarding the prediction of the most stable chair axial-axial conformation, and has larger O–O (1.584 vs 1.564 Å) and C–O bond lengths (1.375 vs 1.391 Å), while C–Cl bond lengths are equal. The energy difference is 9.8 kcal mol⁻¹.

Geometrical optimization :

The heats of formation of 1,2-dioxane and its di- and tetra-halogenated derivatives, determined by means of the AM1 method, are given in Table 5 and which shows the energy differences between both the conformers. The bond lengths, bond angles and dihedral angles values given by the different methods are collected in Table 6.

The stability order of 1,2-dioxane and its halogenated derivatives can be understood through the consideration of four main features. (a) The lone-paired electrons pair-lone-paired electron, arising from the repulsions among the localized lone-paired electrons on the vicinal oxygen atoms. Assuming a tetrahedral hybridization for the oxygen atom, repulsions between 1,2-lone-pair electron pairs are lower in the twist conformation than in the chair conformation. This effect reveals itself via anomalous values for the bonding angles, with the increasing of the O–C–C and X–C–X bond angles. Thus, this effect contributes to the stabilization of the twist form. (b) Torsion angles around the O–O bond favor the twist conformation, since this is the less tightened conformation and the torsion angle in a non-cyclic system is around 100°. (c) The steric effect in the 3,6-

disubstituted derivatives. (d) The interaction between lone-paired electrons of different non-adjacent atoms. This effect is more important for disubstituted dioxanes.

Table 5. Heats of formation (kcal mol⁻¹) for the 1,2-dioxane and halogen substituted 1,2-dioxanes

Substituent	AM1		MNDO-PM3	
	Twist	Chair	Twist	Chair
1,2-Dioxane	-30.66	-32.86	-43.24	-35.58
Tetrafluoro-1,2-dioxane	-237.20	-236.20	-241.30	-241.58
Tetrachloro-1,2-dioxane	-32.99	-33.10	-50.52	-51.44
3,6-Difluoro-1,2-dioxane	-131.17	-135.56	-132.96	-135.23
3,6-Dichloro-1,2-dioxane	-39.04	-40.28	-45.39	-47.78

Table 6. Geometrical parameters of dioxane obtained from different theoretical molecular orbital methods^a

Conformer	Methods	Bonds length (Å)		Bond angle (deg)		
		O–O	C–O	O–O–C	X–C–X	φ ^o
Chair	<i>Ab initio</i> ^b	1.472	1.466	105.64	110.14	-75.3
	AM1	1.290	1.447	112.42	110.71	-66.3
	PM3	1.574	1.391	108.52	108.35	-63.5
Twist	<i>Ab initio</i> ^b					
	AM1	1.286	1.450	112.86	109.70	72.0
	PM3	1.563	1.395	108.45	107.93	72.7

^aRef. 6. ^bφ Torsion angle (C–O–O–C). ^b4-31G basis set.

Table 7. Electronic charges and dipolar moments of tetraderivatives

	4Cl		4F	
	AM1	PM3	AM1	PM3
X ₁	-0.017	0.041	-0.147	-0.121
C ₂	0.084	0.028	0.381	0.339
C ₃	-0.291	-0.306	-0.316	-0.312
C ₄	-0.291	-0.306	-0.316	-0.312
C ₅	0.084	0.028	0.381	0.339
O ₆	-0.097	-0.094	-0.146	-0.125
O ₇	-0.094	-0.094	-0.147	-0.125
X ₈	-0.061	-0.021	-0.166	-0.140
H ₉	0.192	0.175	0.198	0.181
H ₁₀	0.192	0.175	0.196	0.178
X ₁₁	-0.061	-0.021	-0.166	-0.140
X ₁₂	-0.017	0.041	-0.147	-0.121
H ₁₃	0.192	0.176	0.196	0.178
H ₁₄	0.192	0.176	0.198	0.181
μ(D)	1.3533	1.1292	1.7454	1.5421

When analysing the 3,3,6,6-tetrafluoro-1,2-dioxane molecule we verified the twist conformation to be the most stable one (i.e. it has the lowest total electronic energy) according to the AM1 method. But the PM3 method predicts the chair conformation to be the most stable structure. The effect between the 1,2-lone-pair electrons and the torsion angle plays a main role in the determination of the stability via the AM1 method.

Table 8. Electronic charges and dipolar moments of the disubstituted derivatives

	2Cl		2F	
	AM1	PM3	AM1	PM3
X ₁	-0.121	-0.097	-0.180	-0.156
C ₂	-0.035	0.0003	0.104	0.119
C ₃	-0.295	-0.297	-0.315	-0.301
C ₄	-0.295	-0.297	-0.315	-0.301
O ₅	-0.119	-0.114	-0.155	-0.140
C ₆	-0.035	0.0003	0.104	0.119
O ₇	-0.119	-0.114	-0.155	-0.140
H ₈	0.222	0.183	0.203	0.161
X ₉	-0.121	-0.097	-0.180	-0.156
H ₁₀	0.172	0.162	0.172	0.157
H ₁₁	0.176	0.163	0.172	0.160
H ₁₂	0.176	0.163	0.172	0.160
H ₁₃	0.172	0.162	0.172	0.157
H ₁₄	0.222	0.183	0.203	0.161
μ(D)	1.1656	1.0247	1.3349	1.2393

When the four substituents are chlorine atoms, the more noticeable effect is the repulsion of the lone-pair electrons belonging to the vicinal oxygen atoms, and it is revealed through the torsion angles effect. The stability of the chair conformation in the 3,6-difluorodioxane is based on the interaction between the fluorine lone-pair electrons with the C–O bonds belonging to the ring and it is expressed in the shortening of the C–O distance and the lengthening of the C–C distance. In opposition to the twist conformation, the C–O bond lengths are equal in the chair conformation. Furthermore, there is a slight shortening of the C–F bond lengths, which suggests the existence of an interaction between the oxygen lone-pair electrons and the C-F bonds.

Regarding 3,6-dichlorodioxane, the most stable is the chair conformer. Notwithstanding, it is not due to the electronic effect discussed before. In fact, the bulky chlorine atom gives rise to a significant steric effect on the ring. Thus, the C–Cl bond length is noticeably greater in the chair conformation than that found in the twist conformation.

Some variations are noted regarding electronic properties of di- and tetra-substituted derivatives of title compounds as predicted by the two semiempirical methods. In fact, in Table 7 it can be verified that negative electronic charges are mainly distributed over carbon atoms and over

oxygen ring atoms and halogen atom at the axial position, as predicted by the AM1 method. However, PM3 predicts a nearly negligible halogen atom contribution. When halogen substituent is fluorine atom the negative charge contributions increase in these compounds, and numerical values are greater for AM1 method than for PM3 method. In a similar fashion, dipolar moment is higher according to AM1 than that predicted by PM3 procedure. In Table 8 we report negative charges over ring carbon atoms and oxygen atoms as well as the substituent at the axial location. Once again, AM1 predicts larger values than those given by the PM3 method and the same happens with dipolar moments. We display in Table 9 energies for a representative set of molecular orbitals corresponding to the ground state of di- and tetra-substituted halogen derivatives.

There is a remarkable degeneracy between the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the preceding one (i.e. HOMO-1) with an energy gap equal to 0.005 eV, which is rather low for a semiempirical method and which could indicate a relatively high oxidative power for these compounds. This property is based on the easiness to accept one or two electrons, giving rise the oxidation of other molecules in toxic and reactive products. Tetrafluoro derivative presents a lower energy than the corresponding chlorine derivative for HOMO, which suggests a high oxidative capability of the former molecule. Besides, this difference also happens in lowest molecular orbitals, which seems to indicate a relatively larger oxidative power. Identical situation happens in the di-derivatives. In Table 10 we present orbital densities over significative selected atoms ($|C_i| > 0.14$) of halogen tetraderivatives. Although there are differences between contributions due to the coefficient C_i^2 for HOMO orbitals belonging to the tetrafluoro derivative (p_y atomic orbital) and tetrachloro derivative (p_y atomic orbital), both atoms contribute to the corresponding molecular orbital. Consequently, according to this result both the molecules must have similar electronic properties and chemical reactivities.

Conclusions :

We can state that AM1 predicts the chair conformation to be the most stable one for the 1,2-dioxane, which is in line with the *ab initio* calculations. The PM3 describes in a best way the O–O bond length, and also predicts the chair conformation as the most stable one.

Table 9. Energy (in eV) of some molecular orbitals in the ground state for the studied molecules obtained from the AM1 and PM3 methods.

	AM1		PM3		AM1		PM3	
	HOMO	HOMO-1	HOMO	HOMO-1	LUMO	LUMO+1	LUMO	LUMO+1
4F	-0.4435	-0.4494	-0.4804	-0.4832	0.0353	0.0389	-0.0310	0.0283
4Cl	-0.4331	-0.4365	-0.4002	-0.4002	-0.0138	-0.0051	-0.0484	-0.0044
2F	-0.4211	-0.4281	-0.4450	-0.4607	0.0668	0.0884	-0.0075	0.0697
2Cl	-0.4205	-0.4258	-0.3949	-0.3959	0.0287	0.0331	-0.0173	0.0224

Table 10. Orbital densities on selected atoms in HOMO calculated with the AM1 semiempirical method

4F		4Cl	
Atom	Contribution	Atom	Contribution
F _{11s}	0.23827	Cl _{11p_z}	0.33823
C _{21p_y}	0.27617	C _{21p_z}	0.26162
C _{31p_y}	0.28841	C _{31p_z}	0.24901
C _{41p_y}	0.28844	C _{41p_z}	0.24921
C _{51p_y}	0.27684	C _{51p_z}	0.26157
O _{61p_y}	0.41890	O _{61p_z}	0.31918
O _{71p_y}	0.41780	O _{71p_z}	0.31955
F _{81p_y}	0.23287	Cl _{81p_z}	0.33872
H _{101s}	0.18696	H _{101s}	0.14503
F _{111p_y}	0.23348	Cl _{111p_z}	0.33809
F _{121p_y}	0.23878	Cl _{121p_z}	0.33809
H _{131s}	0.18700	H _{131s}	0.11452

With respect to the tetrasubstituted derivatives, the general tendency is maintained with respect to the twist form, although it is not very remarkable. This is a striking disagreement with the available experimental data showing that the chair conformation is the most stable one. These differences can arise from the fact that experiments were made in solution, not in gas phase, so that a direct comparison is not totally rigorous. Since there are not available experimental data in gas phase to make the comparison, we deem suitable to compare them with sound *ab initio* calculations.

The PM3 method describes in a better way the O-O peroxydic bond lengths, and it gives similar results to those arising from *ab initio* calculations so that it seems to be a possible valid way to be able to correlate theoretical calculations with experimental data. The potential barriers chair-twist are best described with the PM3 method.

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